

Usage of Reference Sources in University of Mumbai Library: A Study

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Abstract:

The main aim of this paper is to identify their reference sources of the Knowledge Resource Centre, University of Mumbai and its usage. The purpose of the current study is to make users aware of different types of reference sources and motivate them to use their source to enhance their knowledge. Formerly libraries were regarded as storehouses and books were meant for preservation. Libraries tended to be passive and archival institution. A modern library, with a few exceptions was regarded as a service institution. Its aim is to enable the users to make the most effective use of its resources and services.

Introduction:

A university library is supposed to perform many functions. A university library is a part of a university set-up. Therefore, it exists to serve the objectives of its parent organization. The patrons mainly consist of students, teachers and research scholars.

Occasionally, past students and local community may also form the patrons. Oyewole & Adetimirin (2015) noted that the university library is an integral part of a university established to meet the information and research needs of its students, faculty and staff. These needs are diverse in line with the subject areas offered in the universities. That is why the objectives of university libraries can therefore be as diverse as the institutions themselves (Onuoha, Ikonne & Madukoma 2013). The university library is one created to serve a university. Thus, a university library is regarded as a repository of knowledge and information gateway where information materials are stored (Emwanta & Nwalo, 2013). Faculty members and students will find it very difficult to engage in meaningful research without the contributions of the university library.

University of Mumbai library:

The University of Mumbai was established in 1857. In August, 1864 the University received a donation of Rs.200000 from Mr. Premchand Roychand, a merchant prince of Mumbai, “towards the erection of a University Library which may be an ornament to the city

and by becoming the storehouse of the learner works, not only of the past but of many generations to come, may be means of promoting the high ends of the University.”

Rajabai Tower Library at Fort Campus:

The library is particularly rich in various reference materials, bibliographical tools, books on Mathematics, the Social Sciences and Indology. It also has a valuable and rare collection of back files of periodicals in Sciences, the Social Sciences and Indology.

The access to the Rajabai Tower Library collection is via catalogues except for researchers and teachers who are extended browsing facility, whereas Jawaharlal Nehru Library (JNL), Vidyanagari offers open access i.e. browsing in the stacks for all the readers alike. Fort Library extends membership to undergraduate students as well.

Jawaharlal Nehru Library at the Vidyanagari Campus:

Due to shortage of space another Campus of the University was set up at Vidyanagari in 1968 and a unit of the University Library was constructed in July 1971. The new Library building named Jawaharlal Nehru Library, was constructed and was inaugurated on 18th October 1976 and expanded in phases. Now it functions in a full-fledged manner and caters to the library needs of students, scholars, faculty of all the departments situated on Campus. Today it has a stock of nearly 8 lakhs seventy thousand books, periodicals and other material.

Library collections:

Over the years the Mumbai University Library has not only grown horizontally but also vertically. Emergence of information and communication technology in libraries has enforced the library to amalgamate changes in its collection, services and facilities to meet changing needs and expectations of users. (Garate 2017)

Library Resources	Library Collections
Books	7,92,198
Reference Books	11,668
Current Journals	587
- Indian Journal	172
- Foreign Journal	415
Journals Bound Volumes	77,292
CDS, DVD	257
Subscribe Database	30
E-Journals	10,000
Theses	21,672
Manuscripts	9900

Table 1.1

Library services:

The library provides following services to the users of library.

1. Lending Service
2. Interlibrary Loan Service
3. Reprographic Service
4. Contents pages Service
5. Special Issue Alert
6. Online databases
7. OPAC/WEBOPAC
8. Orientation Programmes /Information Literacy
9. Computer Laboratory

Introduction of Reference sources:

Reference sources are those which are consulted only for getting specific information and which are not meant for continues reading by the users. From this point of view anything may be a reference source. If we get the answer of a query from a specific person, then she/he is also regarded as a reference sources.

Definition of Reference Source:

- o Reference source is generally the book form which is designed by its arrangement and treatment to be consulted for definite items of information, rather than to be read consecutively, and it is a book whose use is restricted to the library building. _ (ALA Glossary).
- o Reference source generally is a book which is consulted for aid or information on a topic, a theme, an event, a person, a data place or a word. _ (Gates).

Importance of Reference Sources:

The importance of reference materials cannot be overemphasized in an academic environment. The use of reference sources is highly beneficial or even indispensable for students to achieve their educational outcomes.

Usage of reference sources:

Reference sources are typically used in two different ways. One use is to get background information on a topic that you are researching. For example, if you use Wikipedia to find out the general history of an event you will be writing about, you are using Wikipedia as a reference source to find out the context of the topic you are researching.

Characteristics of Reference Sources:

- Some of the characteristics of reference books are as follows:
- Information in reference books is presented in order or organized systematically so that it can be searched easily.
- Reference books are exclusively designed to supply the answer to specific queries. In this respect, reference books are planned in a better way than other books. They are a collection of millions of facts and that is way they are called *books of facts*.

Types of reference sources:

There are thousands of reference sources available that cover practically every subject. There are two types of reference Sources

Figure 1

Some reference books are source type which contains the needed information and some directed type. Source type publications provide definite answers to the queries. Example: dictionaries, encyclopaedia's, yearbooks, biographical sources, atlases, geographical sources.

The direction type of sources does not provide definite answers but serve to direct the user to the source of information. They help user in finding the information. Example: indexes and bibliographies.

Figure 2

Dictionaries:

Librarian's Glossary defines dictionary as "A book explaining the words of a language, the words being arranged in alphabetical order. It usually gives the orthography, punctuation and meaning of the word."

- **Types of dictionaries:** There are wide ranges and variety of dictionaries. They can divide into various types, according to their nature and scope of the contents. Figure 3 shows the various types of dictionaries.

Figure 3

Encyclopedias:

The word Encyclopedia originated from the Greek word *Cyclo* and *pedi* which means circle or a complete system of learning, i.e. all-round educational sources.

➤ **Types of Encyclopaedias:** Encyclopedias are generally divided into two types

Figure 4

General encyclopaedia provides a broad overview of many topics of general interest for example, Encyclopaedia Britannica. Subject specific encyclopaedia's deal with specific subject field. They cover different disciplines such as science and technology, medicine, etc. such encyclopaedia provides more in-depth information about a subject.

Yearbooks:

The yearbook is a compendium of current information about the previous year. It is called *compendium* because it provides brief or concise information on a number of topics.

Type of Yearbooks: A yearbook can be divided into two groups, general and supplements to encyclopaedias.

Figure 5

Directories:

ALA Glossary defines directory as “a list of persons or organizations systematically arranged, usually in alphabetical or classed order, giving addresses, affiliation, etc.

- **Types of Directories:** Directories can be divided broadly into two groups’ one is general directories which includes information on international, national/regional, local level another is specific directories which cover information on scientific and learned societies, business, trade, professionals and like groups.

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Figure 6

Handbooks and Manuals

Handbooks and manuals are subject area tools. Handbooks provide information about facts, terms, concepts, etc. of a topic. Manuals provide detailed instruction on a particular subject, such as how to do something or how something work.

➤ **Types of handbooks:** Handbooks are of the following types:

Figure 7

Bibliographies:

A bibliography is a systematically produced descriptive list of records.

○ **Types of Bibliographies:** The bibliographies can be divided into the following types according to its nature, contents and purpose (figure 8)

Figure 8

Abstracts:

According to ALA Glossary, “Abstract is a concise summary that gives the essential points of a book, pamphlet or article.” According to Herbert Menzel and others, “An abstract, simply defined is a condensation that presents succinctly the objectives, scopes, and finding of a document

Types of Abstracts: Abstract are of two types:

Figure 9

News Digest:

These sources are referred to quite frequently by the reference librarians to answer questions-relating to current event.

○ **Types of News Digest:** It can be divided into various types shown below

Figure 10

Indexes:

The word “index” is derived from the Latin word *indicare*. It means “to point” or “to show” the information where it is available.

➤ **Types of Indexes:** the main purpose of all the indexes is to guide the user to the subject content and the physical location of the document. But in terms of types, they vary with each other. The indexes are of the following types:

Figure 11

Biographical Sources:

The term ‘biography’ has been derived from two Greek words *bios* meaning life and *Graphen* meaning to write. It means that biography is a written life sketch of a person.

Type of Biographical Sources: The different types of biographical sources are given below.

Figure 12

- **Individual Biography:** it includes autobiographical sources.
- **Collected Biography:** gives a descriptive account of lives of a large number of eminent persons. It is further divided into the following types:
 - **General/ Universal/ International Biographies:** These contain biographies of persons from all countries.
 - **National/Local Sources:** These cover persons from one particular country or region or area.
 - **Subject or professional Sources:** These cover persons from specific occupations

Statistical Sources:

Statistical sources are important sources of information, especially for the researchers and planners. They provide information about quantitative data. Statistical is an outcome of the collection, classification, analysis and interpretation of the numerical data.

○ **Types of Statistical Sources:** there are number of statistical sources available for providing reference service in the library. These sources can be divided into general and specific sources.

Figure 13

Geographical Sources:

Geographical sources are important sources of information which provide information about places such as cities, towns, lakes, rivers, forests etc. regarding their locations, distances, description and other details.

➤ **Types of Geographical Sources:** these can be divided into two categories; general reference sources (other sources such as yearbooks, encyclopaedia's etc.) and geographical sources (specific).

Figure 14

Electronic Reference Sources:

According to Paul Glister, “digital literacy is the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide range of sources when it is presented via computers.” The increase of electronic resources has had a significant impact on the way the academic community uses stores and preserves information

Reference Sources on CD-ROM:

Nowadays, a number of reference sources are available on digital media such as CDROMs etc. Reference books have appeared on the web in considerable numbers.

Online Databases:

Database is an organized set of data in a particular area or subject. It can be searched through computer automatically. A database is a collection of information that is organized so that it can easily be accessed, managed and updated.

○ **Type of databases:** These databases can be classified according to the types of contents such as bibliographical, full text, numeric and images. These databases can be both offline and online.

1. Bibliographic databases consists of:

- (a) **Numeric databases:** It contains numeric or statistical data.
- (b) **Full text databases:** It contains the full text of a publication/article.
- (c) **Research in progress databases:** It contain description of research in progress

2. Non-bibliographic databases: These are directory type and concerned with business, industrial data, economic, banking, etc.

3. Catalogue record databases: These are online computerized catalogue of national Congress is a good source to search for sources in humanities.

○ **Features of Online Databases:** some of the features of online database are as follows:

- 1. Instant and personalized
- 2. Comprehensive
- 3. Short range
- 4. Long range

Need and Purpose of Study:

This study aims to identify their reference sources of KRC, University of Mumbai Library and its usage. The purpose of the current study is to make users aware about different types of reference sources and motivates them to use these sources to enhance their knowledge.

Aim of the study:

The aim of the present study is find out the usage of reference sources in Knowledge Resource Centre, University of Mumbai Library.

Objectives of the study:

- 1. To find out available reference sources in library.

2. To make users aware about available reference sources.
3. To identify the usage of reference sources
4. To study the purpose of using reference sources in library.
5. To identify the difficulties facing by the users.

Scope and Limitations of the study:

The study covers two Campuses of University of Mumbai. Knowledge Resource Centre, the fort Campus Library called Rajabai Tower Library and Kalina Campus Library called Jawaharlal Nehru Library. The data was collected from only users who visit libraries with random sampling method.

Research methodology:

Keeping in the view of object of the study, the case study method and descriptive method were used. Questionnaire method was use for data collecting and analysed with statistical method. The population of this study consisted of visitors to KRC: JNL & Fort Library.

Literature Review

Reference Sources:

Pressley & Yun (2013) described that “Reference sources are authoritative works that help you locate information about people, facts and ideas. These sources can help you find the date of an important event, major achievements of an individual or organization, or a definition of a term or concept. These books are often used to find specific facts, rather than written to be read cover-to-cover, so they are often held in a special part of the library to be used for a short period of time rather than checked out to a user over a period of days”.

McEnery (2018) viewing “Reference sources can provide general background information (fact, definitions, dates, details), assistance in focusing your topic quick access to important factual and statistical information and reference to other sources of information. It is therefore a good place to begin your research”.

Reference Collection:

Colson (2007) study the determining use of an academic library reference collection. A small academic library did a five-year re-shelving study to guide in collection management. Finding shows 12% of reference collection was heavily used, 17% was moderately used, and 36% was lightly used and 35% are no response. During the five-year dotting project the use of print reference collection was decline and in electronic resources of library subscription only World Almanac and oxford reference Online were used.

Kumari & Talawar (2011). Studied the reference sources collection in seven university libraries of Karnataka, questionnaire was distributed to the librarians of seven university libraries under study to collect the necessary data. And present in the form of table. The total users of university libraries of Karnataka are 17435 and reference sources are 10,096. The study given a comparative data analysis about reference sources collection along with their types in seven different libraries in Karnataka and library wise users’ strength with reference sources collection.

King (2012) the study examines the type of reference collection management practices and strategies used by academic ARL, member's online survey was used for gathering information. The survey population included each department head of the 115 academic research libraries included in the ARL. 43(37%) libraries completed the survey. The result indicates that the majority weed their collection regularly and assessing the use of electronic and print reference materials.

Terrell (2015) discussed about why librarians in the field need this much coaxing to be cajoled into weeding their print reference collection in favor of electronic reference resources. Study suggests the library is not an archive, preserving great tomes for posterity-the collection in a library are for use. Study says one need not worry about the "invasion" of e-reference or the "death" of print reference. The two can coexist peacefully and vitally as long as librarians maintain focus on selecting the best material for their reference collection, no matter its format.

Print vs. Online Reference Resources:

Puacz (2005) studies Electronic vs. Print reference sources in public library collection. This study discussed the goal of reference collection, implication of electronic sources, accessibility issues, research resources such as Gale, EBSCO & ProQuest, free web sources, library created resources, all about discussion supports and validates the obvious, combined use of print and electronic reference is both relevant and necessary in public library. Librarians must carefully evaluate the needs of their patron and determine which source, regardless of format, are most appropriate to fill these needs.

Ritchie & Paul (2007) studies print vs. electronic reference sources: implications of an Australian study. Study finded 45.6% respondents used electronic sources and 43.81% respondents used print sources. These results clearly indicated that both electronic and print sources are essential to current practice of Northern Territory Library.

Usage of Reference Sources:

Bossaller & Adkins (2011) Examine attitude student and practitioners toward and use of various reference sources. For finding survey was conducted to students and practitioners. Results show that reference instructions about reference services and sources going online. Librarian seen students use more online references sources then print sources.

Data Analysis:

The data analysis for the present research was done by the help of tabulation and present into the pie diagrams and bar diagrams. The data was interpreted with the help of descriptive statistic method.

Objective1. To find out available references' sources in the library.

Q. Which type of resources do you have?

Table.1.2: Type of resources

Sr. No.	Resources	FL	JNL

1	Books	✓	✓
2	Textbooks	✓	✓
3	Reference Books	✓	✓
4	Journals	✓	✓
5	Manuscripts	✓	✓
6	Newspaper	✓	✓
7	CDs/DVDs	✓	✓
8	Theses & Dissertations	✓	✓

As the table indicates both the libraries have all the resources which mention.

Objective 2: To make user aware about the available reference's sources

User Awareness:

Are you aware about library resources?

Table.1.3: Awareness about Library Resources

Options	Fort		JNL	
	F	%	F	%
Yes	10	71%	45	88%
No	4	29%	6	12%
Total	14	100%	51	100%

Figure.15:

Table.1.3 shows majority of respondents 10(71%) were aware about library resources while 4(29%) were not aware in FL. Table also shows in JNL moreover majority of respondents 45(88%) were aware while 6(12%) were not aware. The ratio of respondents was given in figure.23.

Objective 3: To identify the usages of reference sources.

Usage of Reference Sources:

This section covers information about usage of reference sources in library. Q. Do you use reference sources?

Table.1.4
: Usage of Reference Sources

Options	FL		JNL	
	F	%	F	%
Yes	11	79%	45	88%
No	3	21%	6	12%

Figure.16

Table.1.4 shows how much respondents use reference sources. In both FL and JNL majorities of respondents respectively 11(79%) and 45(88%) use reference sources. While 3(21%) and 6(12%) do not use any reference sources. Figure.28 shows the ratio.

Objective 4: To study the purpose of using reference sources in library.

Purpose of Using Reference Sources

For what purpose do you use reference sources?

Table.15: Purpose of Using Reference sources

Purposes	FL		JNL	
	F	%	F	%
Research Purpose	6	43%	25	49%
Pleasure/recreation	1	7%	15	29%
Writing Project or Assignments	4	29%	28	55%

Increasing Knowledge	8	57%	29	57%
Enhancing Lecture Notes	5	36%	28	55%

Figure.17:

Table.1.5 shows majority of respondents were 8(57%) in FL use reference sources for enhancing knowledge than research purpose were 6(43%) while 5(36%) using for enhancing lecture notes. Also in JNL majority of respondents were 29(57%) enhancing knowledge than writhing project and lecture notes were 28(55%) while 25(49%) using for research purpose. The ratios are given into the figure.37.

Objective 5: To identify the difficulties facing by users.

Do you have any difficulty in using reference sources?

Table.1.6 Difficulties Using Reference Sources

options	Fort		JNL	
	F	%	F	%
Yes	3	21%	24	47%
No	11	79%	27	53%
Total	14	100%	51	100%

Table.30 shows in FL majority of respondents were 11(79%) don't have any difficulties while only 3(21%) have difficulties. And in JNL 24(47%) have difficulties and 27(53%) don't have difficulties.

Q. If yes, than which difficulties do you face in using reference sources?

Table.1.7: Difficulties Faced by Users

Difficulties face in using reference sources	F	%	F	%
Lack of reference staff to assist me	2	14%	23	45%
There are old and irrelevant reference sources for my course	2	14%	23	45%
The reference section is not convenient and conducive for reading	2	14%	21	41%
I don't know how to use reference sources	3	21%	20	39%
I waste a lot of time when searching for reference sources	3	21%	29	57%
The reference librarians are not friendly	1	7%	23	45%
Poor power of supply and internet connection	2	14%	23	45%

Figure.18:

Table.1.7 shows in FL respondents have difficulties in lack of assist, old and irrelevant resource, waste lots of time in searching etc.

Table also shows in JNL library majority of respondents were 29(57%) waste lots of time in searching information than lack of assistance, irrelevant materials reference librarians are not friendly. Figure.38 shows the ratio of difficulties facing by users.

Findings:

Two questionnaires were prepared, one for librarians another for users of library. Major findings are in Knowledge Resource Centre of Mumbai university library have so many types of reference sources and provides online reference sources and databases through library website. Libraries have reference desk to solving the queries of users and provides orientations to how to use online reference sources.

In two main campus of University of Mumbai Library (KRC) sample was randomly selected and distributed questionnaires were distributed From Fort Library (FL) 14 responses were acquired, while from Jawaharlal Nehru Library (JNL) 51 responses were acquired.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

University of Mumbai Library is one of the oldest university libraries in India, Considering the objectives of higher education today, the university library system must shoulder onerous responsibilities. The library not only complements the classroom study but also aids the research.

The users in Mumbai University Library are Masters Students, Research scholars, teachers. They would like to get best information resources and up to date literatures.

That's way university library provides books, periodicals, databases, manuscripts theses and dissertations etc. materials to their users.

The users provide suggestions about best utilization of reference sources staff should be friendly and appropriate, acquire new reference sources, and give orientation to the users.

Though orientation programmers are conducted for all the departments of the university many students do not attend and so are not aware of the rich collection in the library. Teachers do not visit the library often and do not encourage students to use the library

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